

THE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT UNIVERSITY

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Anotation: *The article discusses the possibilities of using word games in the process of teaching a foreign language at a university. The main classifications of games are given, with the main attention being paid to games of a lexical nature. The article substantiates the conditions that allow the most effective use of word games in foreign language classes, and also provides examples of games at different stages of work with students.*

Keywords: *teaching a foreign language, game method of teaching a foreign language, language games, lexical games, adult learning.*

Mastering a foreign language at a university implies the formation of a number of competencies in students. In particular, graduates should be able to communicate orally and in writing in a foreign language and solve problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction.[1] Therefore, students must have certain knowledge (for example, knowledge of language means) and skills (use the formulas of verbal communication, formulate their point of view, etc.), as well as be able to correlate linguistic means with specific situations of intercultural speech communication.[3] The solution of this complex, "global" problem occurs during the entire period of teaching a foreign language at a university and requires the use of rational and effective approaches and technologies, forms and methods of teaching. Knowledge and possession of language means by students, their use in communication depends on how effectively this material was presented, consolidated, worked out. The method that allows:

- a) to motivate students to study the subject,
- b) contributes to the development of language and speech competence,
- c) contributes to faster and stronger assimilation of the material, is a game.

In modern science, games are considered as a method that can be effectively used in teaching a foreign language to both children and adults. It would be appropriate to give classifications of games that will allow you to find out which games can contribute to the development of certain language skills as the following types of games:

1. Lexical.
2. Grammar.
3. Phonetic.

4. Spelling.

5. Creative.

The first four can be classified as so-called language, the purpose of which is the formation of relevant skills. Creative games are complex in nature, they imply the creative application of acquired knowledge and skills in a game situation.[2] The following games can be called "word games" - they are all related to the word, its spelling, meaning, compatibility with other words. Word games allow students to: - expand vocabulary, getting acquainted with new lexical units; - it is stronger to assimilate already familiar lexical units; - work out the spelling of words; - to activate verbal thinking activity; - gets acquainted with the compatibility of lexical units, set expressions phraseological units. Word games include:

1. Anagrams
2. Crosswords
3. Search for words among alphabetic chaos (Wordsearch)
4. "Gallows" (Hangman)
5. "Words" (composing shorter words from one long one, often for a while).
6. "Unscramble" (composing a word from an existing set of letters).
7. Wordchain (compiling a list of words by replacing one letter in each subsequent word, possibly based on definitions).
8. Constructor (composing words from morphemes presented on separate cards).
9. "One letter - many words" (students name the words they know for a certain letter of the alphabet).
10. "Last letter" (name a word that begins with the last letter of the previous one; it is worth noting that in English, taking into account the unpronounceable -e at the end of a word, it may be suggested to start a word with the last sound of the previous one).
11. "Missing letters" (guess the word only by vowels / consonants).
12. Hot Chair (guess the word by its definition, synonyms, antonyms, etc.) and others.

Some of the games involve group work, team competition (for example, Hot Chair, Constructor, etc.), some work in pairs; such games as "Gallows", "Anagrams", "Wordchain" are appropriate to carry out frontally, presenting the material on the board.[4]

It is necessary to encourage students to express ideas in a foreign language, so they are involved in communication, work out the skills of constructing sentences, certain speech formulas. And in this case, the use of the game in a foreign language lesson actually becomes an effective technique.

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